

An advance Krypton – CO₂ cascade refrigeration unit for the Phase III Upgrade of the VELO detector at CERN

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ABSTRACT

The Vertex Locator (VELO) of the LHCb (Large-Hadron Collider) experiment will soon experience the Phase III upgrade to fully readout events in higher irradiated environment. An unprecedented amount of radiation would lead to temperature levels not manageable by the current CO₂ cooling system (2PACL) developed at CERN-Nikhef. Therefore, a new environmental-friendly cooling medium and working cycle must be designed to fulfill the new requirements with temperature levels expected in the range -60 to -80°C. The noble gas Krypton is the most promising coolant for the future upgrade of the Large Hadron Collider.

This work discussed a potential solution for the heat rejection that can be achieved by a cascade configuration system which comprises a CO₂ cooling unit with multi-evaporating temperature levels. Such process must be reliable and stable, regardless the amount of heat rejected which will vary throughout the lifetime of the detectors.

Keywords: Refrigeration, Carbon Dioxide, Krypton, transcritical, supercritical.

1. INTRODUCTION

The silicon detectors used at CERN to reconstruct the tracks of charged particles in collider experiments need to operate at stable temperature to avoid the phenomena of the thermal runaway and minimise the radiation effect on their performance (Moll et al. (2006)). The Large Hadron Collider at CERN will experience a future upgrade according to the High Luminosity programme (HL-LHC) starting in 2026. This upgrade is planned to increase the luminosity, i.e., the density of the particles created by the collision. This will become more and more critical because of the damage on the silicon sensor leading to different magnitude of the leakage currents, potentially inducing overheating and thus requiring colder temperatures to maintain the leakage currents at acceptable levels (Brüning O (2022)).

CO₂ has been the cooling choice at CERN since 2008 when it was for the first time implemented in the Velo detector. The environmental policy adopted at CERN together with thermo-hydraulic performance of CO₂ have played a fundamental role (Verlaat et al. (2008)). The cooling system rely on a concept namely 2PACL (two-phase accumulator pumped loop) that was specifically developed for the thermal management of the silicon detectors (Verlaat et al. (2008); Verlaat (2007)).

For the future cold temperature range (-70 to -80°C) (Group (2020)) a new high performing working fluid will be required. Thermal analysis of different candidates in the ultra-low temperature range (below the CO₂ freezing point) is particularly important to identify the best coolant, in first approximation from the fluid-perspective only (Contiero et al. (2022)). Indeed, also the mechanical support around the cooling lines needs to be optimized. The noble gas Krypton is the most promising refrigerant for the new temperature range of investigation. Considering the gradual cooling required from ambient conditions down to the cold area together with the thermophysical properties of Krypton, a new hybrid cycle was proposed (Contiero and Barroca (2022)). As occurring nowadays with the 2PACL, a complex cascade system is proposed in order to address the large amplitude of heat rejection required by the Krypton cooling system (considered as low-temperature circuit in the cascade configuration).

2. CHALLENGES FOR THE NEW EVAPORATIVE COOLING SYSTEM

The current cooling system for silicon detector relies on the principle called 2-Phase Accumulator Controlled Loop (2PACL). Figure 1 shows the concept: the cycle works entirely from the warm to the cold area only in the liquid and two-phase area. The required cooling at room temperature operation can be provided in a controlled manner by transferring the cycle in a completely liquid state: the accumulator is heated above the saturation pressure of the environment causing liquefaction of the CO₂ in the loop. In this way, the detector can be gradually cooled down without any thermal shocks of the sensitive

components while protecting the pump from the risk of cavitation. The setpoint in the detector, regardless the power from experiments is on or off, is changed via the accumulator. The accumulator provides an ideal way to controlled precisely and remotely the outlet temperature of the two-phase returning from the detector, considering low pressure drops on the return line to the plant. The amount of cooling provided to the detector is entirely managed by the 2PACL independently from the primary CO₂ transcritical system.

Figure 1: Concept of the 2PACL CO₂ cooling unit (Verlaat et al. (2019)).

As it can be seen in Figure 2 by further cooling the accumulator the pressure can be controlled by the saturation temperature. The only requirement is to have a two-phase mixture under all the operation. The return two-phase flow from the detector must be condensed and subcooled before entering the pump: considering the margin of subcooling, the lowest possible evaporating temperature is $\approx -45^{\circ}\text{C}$. The biggest challenge is therefore represented by the several degrees of subcooling that the pump experiences at the inlet: if the setpoint in the accumulator is further reduced, the primary cooling system needs to operate very close to the freezing limit ($\approx -56^{\circ}\text{C}$). This harsh limit affects the minimal operational temperature of the 2PACL.

Figure 2: Cycle description in the p-h diagram of CO₂ for two different setpoints in the detector(Verlaat et al. (2019)).

In the perspective of a future Upgrade of the LHC, the operational temperature will be lower but still requiring cooling starting from ambient conditions even though for only few times during the detector lifetime. The already existing 2PACL has already been pushed to its limit, represented by the CO₂ triple point. One of the main reason to use CO₂ as coolant for the thermal management of the detectors was the high thermal performance in small channels (Verlaat and Petagna (2019)), besides other factors (i.e. environmental-friendly). However, the thermo-hydraulic performance of the fluid starts degradating by operating at low reduced pressures because of the larger pressure and temperature drops, as well as low heat transfer coefficients. Therefore, in order to operate at high reduced pressures in the new temperature range (-60 to -80°C) the cooling at ambient conditions will start in supercritical state as it happens for the new fluid candidate Krypton, requiring a completely new cycle (Contiero and Barroca (2022)).

3. THE KRYPTON COOLING CYCLE

Figure 3 illustrates the pressure - enthalpy diagram for Krypton. The green line represents the room temperature at which the system will start operating, prior to start-up. To gradually cool the detector from ambient conditions down to the cold area, a supercritical cooldown cycle is required: if cold liquid is delivered to the detector a thermal shock would occur. The starting area is in supercritical state where pressure – temperature are independent on each other. However, in supercritical state the pressure in the high side is determined by the relationship between refrigerant charge, volume and temperature. Here, compared to a two-phase system, one extra degree of freedom is gained: by charging the system, while cooling the high-pressure side by rejecting heat to the high-temperature CO₂ circuit of the cascade system, the cycle can be conditioned to operate at high pressures, almost nearly-isobaric. The distance between the isothermal lines represent the specific heat capacity: by operating at high pressures those isothermal lines are nearly vertical, protecting the detector from a fast overcooling.

Figure 3: P-h diagram for Krypton with some important isothermal lines highlighted.

Silicon detector cooling must always work, even if the detector power is switched off. As described already, the cold area operation must be reached very slowly with a cooling target of 1 K/min (common practise in particle detectors). To comply

with those requirements, a new cycle was designed (Contiero and Barroca (2022)) and it is showed in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Simplified PI&D of the hybrid Krypton cooling system.

The system as it occurs for the 2PACL must be oil-free to operate safely in the highly-irradiated environment. Indeed, if some oil droplets reach the detectors, those droplet could polymerize and potentially clog the pipes which would be unacceptable as reliability is the main priority. Therefore the system rely on oil-free turbomachine. The hybrid cycle also comprises a gas cooler section where the heat is rejected to the CO₂ primary system at different evaporating temperature levels, requiring a continuous regulation of the suction pressure. Indeed, the primary system is responsible for removing the heat and maintain the secondary loop stable and therefore it shall be able to react quickly to transient regimes. An internal heat exchanger is located downstream the gas cooler section to supply the necessary superheat at the compressor suction port while is operating in the cold area (transcritical cycle). The high-pressure is controlled via ejector, which acts also a recirculating device for the stream flow at the detector outlet. This works similarly to a traditional ejector vapor compression system during transcritical conditions (Elbel and Lawrence (2016)). The evaporator loop (blue line) is almost-fully passive due to restricted access in the underground cavern and the use of any active component would be unacceptable in case of malfunctioning. The only active control is performed via a bypass on the subcooled liquid line which serves as regulator to allow the boiling starting at the entrance of the evaporator. The detector comprises multiple cooling lines where each of them has a dedicated expansion device (capillary tube). The accumulator will act as a storage volume during supercritical conditions while as a separator during transcritical.

3.1 Supercritical cycle: start-up

The start-up represents the first challenge to overcome (Figure 5). The detector are light-weight with an extreme low mass and a heat capacity which is not uniform over all the structure. The required cooling power to lower their temperature by 1 K/min is therefore unknown: in this sense controlling the fluid temperature is the best way to ensure a gradual and

controlled cooling. Indeed, by delivering to the detector slightly colder fluid in a controlled manner it will be possible to bring the detector into the cold area without thermal shocks. First the system can be charged via the high-pressure tank (filled with supercritical Krypton) to the desired pressure level and then the compressor can start. Mainly during the startup the triangle cycle (A-B-C) gives an extra degree of freedom. Part of the Krypton flow cooled by the first CO₂ gas cooler (B-C) is throttled back to the suction line: in this way the motive flow rate through the ejector can be accurately controlled and consequently the ejector geometry can be adjusted to fulfill the required cooling rate to the detector. By further cooling the high-pressure side the pressure will start falling and therefore extra charging would be needed to maintain an isobaric gas cooling process. The high-pressure side is cooled down by the primary CO₂ cooling system to -50°C, which would represent the lowest possible evaporating temperature on the primary circuit of the cascade system. The regulation of the motive nozzle through a regulating needle increases the flexibility of the unit, allowing to achieve the desired cooling rate during start-up and at the same time it offers a precise control of the detector outlet during flow boiling conditions (transcritical regime) without the need for colder temperatures. By doing so, the future cascade system for cooling of the silicon detector can remain fully environmental-friendly.

Figure 5: Cycle representation in the p-h diagram during start-up.

3.2 Transcritical operation

Once the detector is cooled down to approximately -50°C, the pressure in the cycle can be lowered. Throttling more flow through the CGBV will push the suction pressure down and the high-pressure will follow accordingly. However, during all of these transient scenarios, it is crucial to regulate the motive flow area of the ejector. This is particularly important in the region above the critical point, where the isothermal lines have a different shape. In this case, decreasing the suction pressure would result in a colder fluid for the same pressure decrease, in contrast to the right-hand side of the diagram where the temperature lines are nearly vertical. Once the transition from supercritical to subcritical takes place, the tank that previously functioned as an accumulator turns into a phase separator. Figure 6 illustrates the cooling concept based on the hybrid ejector-vapor compression system. The liquid receiver separates the liquid (G) and the vapor phase (N). The vapor is first superheat in the internal heat exchanger before being compressed (N-A-B). The hot gas at the compressor discharge is cooled down by the CO₂ primary chiller (B-C). The receiver pressure can be actively controlled by the CGBV (cold-gas bypass

valve) (C-A). This implies that the compressor rack must be oversized to ensure that there is always a degree of freedom for regulation, particularly given the broad range of suction conditions that the compressor rack experiences during the start-up procedure. This in turn induces a fixed flow rate through the second gas cooler and ejector. On the low-pressure loop (green), the achieved temperature-pressure profile is the outcome of two factors: on one hand the thermo-hydraulic performance of the fluid, on the other hand the Krypton flow undergoing the boiling process. The setpoint, considered as normally happens in refrigeration as the outlet pressure of the evaporator, can be controlled indirectly via the ejector. Indeed, the expansion work available is mainly dependent on the conditions at the motive inlet: considering a constant flow as result of the regulation of the CGBV, the throat of the motive area is adjusted to reach the pressure level required to suck the required flow rate and therefore controlling the detector outlet, as result of the passive pressure development along the loop. Being two-phase, controlling the detector outlet pressure means to control the detector temperature.

Figure 6: Cycle representation in the p-h diagram during transcritical operation (power from the detector ON).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study addressed the challenges that would arise from the future upgrade of the LHC, and proposed a new cooling system using Krypton as the most effective coolant for High Energy Physics experiments, as previously shown in another study. The new system differs from the current CO₂ cycle in use, but still adheres to the detector requirements that remain unchanged and serve as the basis for the future system's design. The design focuses on three operating scenarios, including start-up in a supercritical state, transition from supercritical to subcritical conditions at the detector inlet, and cold operation in a transcritical refrigeration cycle. The system's operating mode and control logic vary according to the detector temperature. In addition, to enable remote control of the detector outlet conditions as occurs for the 2PACL system, a possible control strategy based on parallel regulation of the CGBV-modulating ejector was analyzed. As part of this comprehensive study, numerical modelling of the supercritical cooldown process and transcritical cycle is still ongoing, and a small prototype using Xenon (noble gas with similar properties of Krypton) in warmer conditions is currently under construction to test the Krypton unit's cooling concept.

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